

Forced-Convection Cooling Using a Vortex Tube for Metal Flat Plate Shape

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Abstract—This experimental paper aims at measuring the cooling time and associated effects for an aluminum flat plate by modifying the angle of impact. This experimentation is done by using a small-size vortex tube experimental kit from Meech with the GREEN generator. The work has been done as a part of my Bachelor of Engineering Honors degree during my honors project in 2021-2022. A CFD analysis has been carried on to show the heat propagation around the plate when cooling.

Index Terms—Vortex Tube, Ranque-Hilsch, Thermodynamics, Heat Transfer, CFD, Fluid Mechanics

I. INTRODUCTION

A vortex tube, also called a Ranque-Hilsch tube, is an instantaneous thermodynamic system. By applying compressed air at ambient temperature and pressure of about 7 to 8 bar at the inlet, the vortex tube produces two air flows at different temperatures instantly [1]. The first one is colder and the second one is hotter than the inlet [2]. Vortex tubes are widely used in industry for local cooling especially to cool down data servers, electronic devices, or highly explosive atmospheres. Vortex tubes are cheap, low maintenance, and highly reliable due to no moving parts. The experimental setup (fig1) is made by a vortex tube from Meech, a flat aluminum plate, and a thermocouple.

The vortex tube used was the experimental kit of Meech with the GREEN generator [3], two cylinders of the same shape and size from aluminum and stainless steel, and one thermocouple.

II. METHODS

The thermocouple was placed under the plate to avoid external perturbations as much as possible. The thermocouple was linked to the software Squirrel View to collect the data and export it to a CSV format for further post-data treatment [6]. The properties of the vortex tube (-28°C, 1.9 m/s) have been found experimentally [3]. The compressor was set to 8 bars of pressure. 3 sets of measurements (10, 45, and 90 degrees) have been done for the same aluminum flat plate and the same initial temperature 53°C. The CFD analysis has been carried out by Ansys

Fig. 1. Experimental Set-up

Mechanical 2022 with a transient 3D code. A hexahedron mesh grind has been chosen. The parameters in the CFD analysis differ from the experiment to have a better understanding of the heat propagation by having wilder conditions. The initial temperature was set to 200°C, the jet stream temperature to -46°C running parallel to the plate and the heat transfer coefficient has been calculated from semi-empirical method [4] around $168 \text{ W.m}^{-2}.\text{K}^{-1}$. The assumption that there is no heat radiation toward the surface has been made to make the calculation easier.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The greater the jet impact angle, the better the heat transfer (fig.2). This experience follows the prediction of semi-empirical method calculation [5]. To cool down the same metal for the same DT and specifications, the 10 degrees angle takes around 105s, the 45 degrees around the 90s, and the 90 degrees is around the 80s. The temperature gradient of the plate (fig.3) for t (0; 105; 210; 315) [s] is decreasing along the x-axis due to the cooling. The fluid is heated alongside the x-axis in contact with the metal while the metal cools down. The longer the air stays in contact, the smaller the dT between the fluid and

the plate, and the lower the energy transfer. Resulting of this process, a gradient of temperature alongside the plate is existing.

Fig. 2. Cooling time in Function of the Angle

IV. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study has been done to compare 3 different angles of impact for cooling an aluminum flat plate by a vortex tube. The results show that the bigger the angle of impact, the higher the heat exchange rate. Choosing a 90-degree orientation in the industry is crucial. This difference of 25 seconds is huge when adding up to a big number of parts that need to be cooled down.

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Fig. 3. Cooling time a the flat plate for t (0; 105; 210; 315) [s].